

The Major Role of the Sales Force in the Relationship Between Customer Orientation and the Sales Performance of Insurance Company Intermediaries

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 19 May 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: BOUDAD Dounia</p>	<p>The objective of this article is to assess the role of customer orientation on the sales performance of insurance company intermediaries and to test the mediating role of sales force management in this influence. The literature on customer orientation and performance reveals that the majority of research has focused on Western companies. No research has examined the role of sales force management in the relationship between customer orientation and the sales performance of insurance company intermediaries in developing countries. Following a qualitative study conducted with eight insurance broker managers, a quantitative questionnaire-based study was conducted with 84 managers. Structural equations and regression analysis were useful in analyzing and processing the data, as well as in testing the direct and indirect link between customer orientation and sales performance. The results show that customer orientation positively influences sales performance and that sales force management plays a partial mediating role.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Customer orientation; sales performance; management; sales force; mediating role.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

To ensure its survival and development, a company must constantly adapt and be efficient and profitable, which requires greater professionalization of its human resources (Ailli, 2011). Among the factors of a company's overall effectiveness, human effectiveness can be highlighted, that is, the ability of people to implement a strategy and make the organization function. Human effectiveness is the result of the union of competent, motivated, and communicative people, particularly its sales force, an important factor in commercial effectiveness. Some authors (Spiro et al., 2003; Zeyl et al., 2011) define sales force management as the management of sales personnel, considered a component of an organization's marketing program. This definition takes into account the close relationship between marketing and sales, which has led some authors to consider sales forces as an integral part of marketing, enabling the marketing plan to be implemented by generating sales revenue (Ailli, 2011). Sales force management is, due to its cross-functional nature between marketing and human resources, a highly sought-after field of study among researchers. Given the

central role that salespeople occupy in sales dynamics, the desire to learn more about them remains a concern for researchers, as they contribute to the company's commercial performance (Eyeghe, 2018).

According to Narver and Slater (1990), customer orientation corresponds to a good understanding of the value chain of different end-consumer segments. It corresponds to the acquisition of customer information, the ongoing understanding of their value chain (Day and Wensley, 1988), and the identification of their latent or expressed needs (Narver and Slater, 1990). For Pekovic and Rolland (2012), customer orientation is thought of in terms of collecting, sharing, and using customer data and in terms of implementing coordinated initiatives based on this data.

According to Ouattara (2007), commercial performance is defined as a company's ability to satisfy its customers by offering them high-quality goods and services that meet their expectations. According to Plauchu and Tairou (2008), commercial performance is the art of being present with the right person at the right time, with a relevant offer, which

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allows for the establishment of lasting and profitable business relationships for the company in a context of constant pursuit of service excellence. For Sogbossi (2010), customer satisfaction is performance linked to the satisfaction of the company's customers.

Satisfaction must be a constant concern for managers, as it constitutes a pillar of the company's financial sustainability (Bughin, 2006).

According to Saxe and Weitz (1982), customer orientation is understood in the sales force's behavior by seeking to adjust it to benefit customer satisfaction, customer retention, and individual sales performance. A customer-oriented company thus strives to create greater value for its customers by analyzing their needs and preferences, thereby gaining a competitive advantage and improving the company's sales performance (Zhu and Nakata, 2007).

Customer orientation characterizes salespeople who want to satisfy their customers and build long-term relationships with them. Customer-oriented salespeople more easily close sales when they use influence principles, and this does not harm the quality of the relationship with their customers. This has important implications for sales culture, training, control systems, and salesperson compensation (Banikema and Julienne, 2017).

Although previous studies (Gotteland et al., 2007; Pekovic and Rolland, 2012; and Gafa, 2020) have provided a comprehensive description of the link between market orientation and performance, to our knowledge, no empirical research has examined the mediating role of sales force management on the specific impact of customer orientation on sales performance among insurance brokers in the Moroccan context.

Insurance brokers act as intermediaries between their clients and insurance companies. Their goal is to provide the best insurance policies for their clients. Firstly, he must therefore define the needs of his clients, whether they are individuals or professionals.

A literature review shows that a more in-depth study of the relationships between customer orientation and business performance is necessary (Zhu and Nakata, 2007). For Pekovic and Rolland (2012), the effect of customer orientation on the company's business performance has not yet been fully studied at the empirical level, although the literature is constantly expanding. It should be noted that some authors (Gotteland et al., 2007; Pekovic and Rolland, 2012) have recommended studying the link between customer orientation and business performance by integrating a mediating variable to observe its effect on this relationship. By aligning with this idea of integrating a mediating variable into the relationship between customer orientation and sales performance, we propose to answer the following question in this study: Does sales force management mediate the influence of customer orientation on sales performance among insurance brokers?

In this article, we successively present a literature review and the hypotheses followed by the research model, the methodology adopted, the research results and their discussions, as well as the various contributions of this research.

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

After establishing the direct relationship between customer orientation and sales performance, we present the indirect relationship between these two concepts through the mediating effect of certain variables.

2.1. The Direct Influence of Customer Orientation on Sales Performance

According to Deshpandé et al. (1993), customer orientation is a set of beliefs that prioritizes customer interests in developing a profitable business over the long term, which is consistent with the idea that a company's success depends on its organizational culture being customer-oriented (Gatignon and Xuereb, 1997). According to Singh and Ranchhod (2004), it is important to invest in customer orientation because it potentially allows the company to be more commercially efficient than its competitors and achieve better results by anticipating market trends and developing product and service strategies that meet customer needs and requirements. In addition, customers face switching costs, which leads to greater customer retention and an advantage for customer-oriented companies. Customer orientation thus allows for better market positioning and consequently, better business performance. Furthermore, as Narver and Slater (1990) point out, companies aiming to build a sustainable competitive advantage must create ever-increasing value for their customers. According to Kennedy et al. (2003), customer orientation enables better market positioning and, consequently, better business performance. A customer-oriented company is better able to provide excellent service quality and generate customer satisfaction (Furrer, 2007), which are considered key indicators of strong business performance.

Several studies have demonstrated the existence of a link between customer orientation and business performance (Hilman and Kaliappen, 2015; Doucouré et al., 2018; Gafa, 2020). A literature review published by Zhu and Nakata (2007) identifies the existence of a negative relationship in some contexts such as the non-profit sector, but the majority of results show that there is a positive effect of customer orientation on performance measures. The positive relationship that exists between customer orientation and business performance is further reinforced by studies that show that the non-opportunistic and flexible nature of customer orientation helps to develop customer trust and commitment, thus creating a competitive advantage (Pekovic and Rolland, 2012). These authors confirm the proposition

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that customer orientation positively influences customer perceptions and ultimately business performance. Other studies provide evidence of a positive relationship, both in terms of market and financial indicators, in the United States (Han et al., 1998), the United Kingdom (Appiah-Adu and Singh, 1998), Japan (Deshpandé et al., 1993) and Turkey (Yilmaz et al., 2005).

Drawing on the arguments and conclusions of the literature reviewed, which repeatedly demonstrate that customer orientation influences a company's commercial performance, we propose to test the following first hypothesis:

H1: Customer orientation positively impacts the commercial performance of insurance company intermediaries.

2.2 The indirect influence of customer orientation on commercial performance.

We previously discussed the direct link between customer orientation and commercial performance. A review of the literature reveals that the direction of this relationship could be affected by various variables. Some authors (Denis et al., 2000; Gotteland et al., 2007) have recommended studying the link between customer orientation and performance by incorporating a mediating or moderating variable to observe its effect on this direct relationship. This prompted researchers to focus more attention on the mediating role of certain variables: the environment and learning phenomena (Slater and Narver 2000), the market environment (Pekovic and Rolland, 2012), membership in a professional organization (Doucouré et al., 2019), the organization of contact personnel (Gafa, 2019), or product-related services (Gafa, 2020).

While Slater and Narver (2000) found that market factors weakly moderate the relationship between customer orientation and performance, Greenley (1995) concluded, working on a sample of English companies, that the influence

of customer orientation on company performance is moderated by the market environment. Similarly, based on a study of 159 hospitals, Kumar et al. (2011) indicate that the positive relationship between customer orientation and various organizational performance measures is moderated by market turbulence, competitive hostility, and supplier power. Furthermore, Kumar et al. (2011) conclude that environmental turbulence and competitive intensity moderate the main effect of customer orientation on firm business performance. Appiah-Adu and Singh (1998) found that market characteristics, such as market dynamism and competitive intensity, do not moderate the impact of customer orientation on business performance. However, Han et al. (1998) suggest that technological developments moderate the relationship between customer orientation and business performance. Given that previous literature demonstrates the need to study the indirect influence of customer orientation on sales performance, we propose to investigate the mediating role of sales force management in the relationship between customer orientation and sales performance. Therefore, we formulate the following second hypothesis:

H2: Sales force management mediates the influence of customer orientation on the sales performance of insurance company intermediaries.

III. CONCEPTUAL MODEL AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The presentation of the conceptual model will be followed by the methodological approach adopted in this research.

3.1. Conceptual Model

The conceptual model of this research will allow us to test the various influences between customer orientation and sales performance.

Our analytical framework is schematically presented as follows:

Figure 1: Conceptual research model

3.2. Qualitative study methodology

Qualitative research is an intermediate step in Churchill's (1979) paradigm and consists of generating statements to construct the survey questionnaire.

The lack of specific research on customer orientation, sales force management, and sales performance in a developing

country context led us to opt for a qualitative approach (Miles and Huberman, 2003). Lacking sufficient insight into the identifiers of these various variables, we favored interviews with an interpretivist stance (Allard-Poesi et al., 2007). These semi-structured interviews, lasting an average of thirty minutes, were conducted with insurance brokerage

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executives and inquired about customer focus, sales force management, and sales performance, respectively, through the following series of questions:

- What do you mean by customer focus? How do you practice customer focus in your company? How important is customer focus for your company?

- What does the concept of sales force suggest to you? What do you mean by sales force management? How do you practice sales force management in the insurance brokerage industry? What is its relevance to your growing business?

- What do you mean by sales performance? How do you measure this sales performance?

The selection of respondents was based on the executives' willingness to answer our questions. The survey was conducted through interviews with eight executives. We

deemed that we had reached saturation and therefore retained only the twelve (8) executives.

Thematic content analysis was the analytical method used for the qualitative phase. This systematic and comparative analysis is essential to overcome the variability of individual discourses and enable access to common meanings. To this end, the content analysis steps recommended by Wacheux (1996) were followed: categorization (coding the text according to the selected themes), inference (explanation of what led the actors to the statement), and interpretation (implications for our research questions).

The table below shows the distribution of the qualitative study sample by seniority and type of executive.

Table 1. Distribution of Executives Interviewed

Company seniority	Less than 5 years old	5 to 10 years	10 to 15 years	15 years and older	Total
Manager	-	2	1	1	4
Sales Manager	2	-	1	1	4
Total	2	2	2	2	8

Source: Survey data

The sample for this survey consisted of 50% managers and 50% sales managers. After inventorying the information collected, we formatted it in writing. This text, called verbatim, represents the raw data from the survey. To transcribe the information, we noted word for word what each interviewee said without editing or abbreviating the text. We grouped information with the same meaning or significance by theme to calculate frequencies for each theme.

Based on the information from the interviews with the managers, we generated items and then conducted a semantic clarity test, the objective of which is to verify and reconcile the clarity of the statements with their ease of understanding; to ensure the correct meaning of the statements, that is, the correct choice of words and expressions. To do this, we interviewed the selected individuals face-to-face. After formulation, we obtain the items for the different variables presented below.

Box 1: Items of the customer orientation measurement scale

- * We know our customers well (OC1)
- * We encourage customer feedback and complaints (OC2)
- * We regularly visit our customers (OC3)
- * We assess customer satisfaction (OC4)
- * We analyze the factors influencing the choice of our services (OC5)
- * We study our customers' needs (OC6)
- * We verify the image of our services among our customers (OC7)
- * We offer our customers services according to their needs (OC8)
- * We respond to customer dissatisfaction (OC9)
- * We provide loyalty benefits to our customers (OC10)
- * We treat our customers according to their category in our files (OC11)

Box 2: Items of the sales force management measurement scale

- * * We define positions when recruiting our salespeople (MF1)
- * * We describe the duties related to each position (MF2)
- * * We conduct tests for candidates (MF3)
- * * We provide general training to our salespeople (MF4)
- * * We provide specific training to our salespeople (MF5)
- * * We organize external training for our salespeople (MF6)
- * * We train our salespeople internally (MF7)
- * * We provide our salespeople with performance-based benefits (MF8)
- * * We evaluate our salespeople's behavior (MF9)
- * * We evaluate our salespeople's revenue collections (MF10)
- * * We promote the best salespeople (MF11)
- * * We mention the working conditions of salespeople (MF12)
- * * We announce the recruitment of salespeople (MF13)
- * * We give bonuses to salespeople based on their performance (MF14)
- * * We compensate salespeople for overtime (MF15)
- * * We evaluate Visits made by our sales representatives (MF16)
- * * We offer bonuses to our sales representatives (MF17)
- * * We encourage teamwork among sales representatives (MF18)
- * * We grant honorary titles to our sales representatives (MF19)
- * * We award commissions to our sales representatives (MF20)

Box 3: Items of the commercial performance measurement scale

- * * Our business revenue is growing (PC1)
- * * Our business profit is growing (PC2)
- * * Customers are satisfied with our services (PC3)
- * * Our services' market share is growing (PC4)
- * * We have a good competitive position in the market (PC5)
- * * Customers are loyal to our services (PC6)

3.3. Quantitative Study Methodology

After presenting the study sample, we present the quantitative data analysis methodology.

3.3.1. Study Sample

In the absence of an exhaustive list of all brokers, this study conducted a simple empirical sample using a snowball

method (convenience sample). A total of 102 brokers were contacted, and in return, we received 84 usable questionnaires, representing a response rate of 82%. The various characteristics of the sample are provided below.

Table 2: Sample Characteristics

Eléments	Variables	Effective	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Size (Employment)	0 - 5 personnes	2	3	3
	5 - 10 personnes	13	15	18
	10 - 15 personnes	32	38	56
	15 - 20 personnes	26	31	87
	Plus de 20 personnes	11	13	100
	Total		84	100
Seniority	6 - 8 ans	6	7	7
	8 - 10 ans	17	20	27
	10 - 12 ans	14	17	44

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	12 - 14 ans	9	11	55
	14 - 16 ans	11	13	68
	16 et plus	27	32	100
	Total	84	100	-
Respondents	Directeur ou Gérant	25	30	30
	Responsable commercial	59	70	100
	Total	84	100	-

* Source: Study data

3.3.2. Analysis Methodology

The approach proposed by Churchill (1979) and revised by MacKenzie et al. (2005) was adopted in this study. Therefore, we applied exploratory factor analysis to the measurement scales. We then conducted a series of principal component analyses, the results of which were consolidated by the significance of the KMO and Bartlett's Sphericity tests. For this purpose, items with factor loadings less than 0.5 (Evrard, Pras, and Roux, 2003) were eliminated. Finally, Cronbach's alpha coefficients were calculated to establish the reliability of the measurement scales. The parameters of the confirmatory factor analysis were estimated using the maximum likelihood adjustment function.

The reliability of our instruments is confirmed by calculating Jöreskog's Rho (1993). To test the mediating effect, we followed Hayes's (2013) approach using Hayes' (2018) PROCESS macro in SPSS.

IV. MAIN RESULTS

We first present the results of the factor analysis, followed by those of the various tests of the study's hypotheses.

4.1. Factor Analysis

The results of the KMO and Bartlett's Sphericity tests are presented in the table below and show that the data from the various scales are factorable.

Table 3. Results of the Kaiser, Meyer and Olkin (KMO) test and the Bartlett test

KMO index and Bartlett test	Customer orientation	Sales force management	Commercial Performance
KMO	0,847	0,853	0,729
Bartlett	839,238	921,714	741,748
(P)	,000	,000	,000

Source: study data

The results of the dimensionality of the measurement scales after removing items with low contributions are summarized in the table below.

Table 4. Eigenvalues and percentages of variances accounted for by factors

Variables	Dimensions	Extraction Sums of squares of the factors retained after removing items with low contribution		
		Eigenvalues	% variance	Cumulative % variance
Customer orientation	Dimension 1	12,781	88,412	88,412
Sales force management	Dimension 1	8,741	30,414	30,414
	Dimension 2	5,918	22,321	52,735
	Dimension 3	4,751	13,814	66,549
	Dimension 4	3,947	11,147	77,696
	Dimension 5	2,714	9,814	87,510
Commercial Performance	Dimension 1	5,741	73,478	73,478

Source: Study data

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The following table presents the factor loadings and commonalities of the items after removing those with low loadings, and the reliability and validity tests of the measurement scales.

Table 5. Factor analysis of the scales

Variables	Dimensions	Items	Factor weight	Communality	Cronbach's Alpha	Rho of Jöreskog	Convergent validity rho
Customer orientation	Customer orientation	OC1	0,67	0,64	0,72	0,83	0,68
		OC2	0,66	0,63			
		OC4	0,71	0,70			
		OC6	0,68	0,67			
		OC8	0,66	0,65			
		OC9	0,70	0,67			
Sales Force Management	Recruitment	MF1	0,72	0,68	0,75	0,77	0,64
		MF2	0,81	0,71			
		MF12	0,77	0,71			
		MF13	0,80	0,75			
	Training	MF4	0,68	0,61			
		MF5	0,70	0,64			
		MF6	0,72	0,66			
	Remuneration	MF8	0,73	0,70			
		MF14	0,68	0,65			
		MF15	0,75	0,71			
		MF20	0,77	0,72			
	Assessment	MF9	0,67	0,63			
		MF10	0,71	0,67			
		MF16	0,74	0,71			
	Motivation	MF11	0,66	0,64			
		MF17	0,71	0,68			
		MF18	0,72	0,70			
	Commercial performance	Commercial performance	PC1	0,74			
PC2			0,94	0,92			
PC3			0,84	0,81			
PC4			0,83	0,80			

Source: study data

Table 6. Correlation between variables

Variables	Correlations between constructs		
	1	2	3
1. Customer orientation	1		
2. Sales Force Management	,647**	1	
3. Sales Performance	,564**	,517**	1

Source: Study data.

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed)

The results in the previous table show that all variables are positively and significantly correlated.

4.2. Testing the Different Hypotheses

We first present the direct influence test and then the

mediation test.

4.2.1. Direct Influence Test

The first hypothesis of this research is tested using regression

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Table 7: The Direct Influence of Customer Orientation on Sales Performance

Model	Standardized Coefficients Beta	Student		ANOVA ^a		R-deux ajusté	Dubin-Watson
		t	Sig.	F	Sig.		
Constant	-	13,724	0,000	17,814	0,000	0,418	2.003
Customer orientation	0,657	11,624	0,000				

Adjustment indices $\chi^2 = 133$; $\chi^2/ dll = 2,5$; GFI = 0,92; AGFI = 0,91; RMSEA = 0,04; NFI = 0,92; CFI = 0,95

Source: Study data

a. Dependent variable: Sales performance

The results in the table above show that the overall model is good and adequately explains the relationship between customer orientation and sales performance. It should also be noted that the standardized Beta coefficient shows that the influence of customer orientation on sales performance is strong. It should also be noted that all fit indicators are satisfactory and demonstrate the good fit of the model to the

data. Therefore, the first hypothesis, H1, is confirmed.

4.2.2. Testing the mediating effect of sales force management

Once the direct relationship is positive and significant, we can proceed to the mediation test. Therefore, we followed Hayes's (2013) approach using his PROCESS macro in SPSS.

Table 8: Results of the sales force management mediation test

Dependent variable	Independent variable	Mediating variable	Regression coefficient	Test value t	95% Bootstrap CI	P-value
Commercial performance	Customer orientation	Sales force management	0,657	11,624	0,0147 ; 0,1617	P< 0,01

Source: Study data

The results in the table above show that customer orientation positively and significantly influences sales performance through sales force management.

Therefore, sales force management mediates the relationship between customer orientation and sales performance. Therefore, hypothesis H2 is supported.

Table 9: Comparison between the partial direct and indirect influence model

Relationships			Direct effect			Indirect effect		
			Estimated value	Valeur de test t	Significanc e	Estimated value	Valeur de test t	Significanc e
Customer orientation	→	Commercial performance	0,443	7,407	***	0,214	5,714	***

Source: Study data ***: Significant at the 1% level

The results in the table above show that the value of the direct effect is greater than that of the indirect effect, taking into account sales force management as a mediating variable between customer orientation and sales performance. Therefore, sales force management plays a partial mediating role between customer orientation and sales performance.

dimensions is highest for compensation, followed by motivation, training, recruitment, and finally, the evaluation dimension.

The results in the table above show that each dimension of sales force management mediates the influence of customer focus on sales performance. The influence of customer focus on sales performance across sales force management

V. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The results of this research show that customer orientation among intermediaries is primarily justified by a good understanding of their customers, the ability to take customer complaints into account, and the prompt response of managers in the event of customer dissatisfaction. Managers are also concerned with satisfying customer needs, which

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demonstrates that they aim for excellent profitability with their customers. It should be noted that they focus on the needs of existing customers in order to better satisfy and retain them. These intermediaries also benefit from customer proximity, creating a relationship of trust between them and their customers, which fosters customer loyalty.

It is important to note that this sector is unique in that they do not conduct market research, often due to their limited financial resources and sometimes their lack of awareness of the importance of such research on the profitability of their businesses. This shows that insurance company intermediaries have some weaknesses when it comes to identifying factors likely to influence the choice of their services. This confirms the results of some previous studies (Tsapi and Tchunte, 2006; Pekovic and Rolland, 2012; Gafa, 2020) which have shown that customer orientation in small organizations is limited to a few actions due to their limited resources.

Furthermore, the research results show that sales force management consists of five dimensions. The "recruitment" dimension is manifested by the definition of sales positions during recruitment, the description of tasks to be performed, the definition of working conditions for sales agents, and the announcement of sales recruitment. The "training" dimension is characterized by general training followed by specific training as well as external training for sales agents. It should be noted that the "remuneration" dimension is manifested by the allocation of commissions and social benefits to sales agents, the granting of bonuses linked to the evolution of the salespeople's work and the remuneration of overtime. As for the "evaluation" dimension, it is achieved through the behavior of salespeople, the total collections and the visits made by sales agents. The "motivation" dimension is constituted by the allocation of promotions to the best sales agents, the granting of sales bonuses and the encouragement of teamwork. All of these results support those of previous studies (Mahé de Boislandelle, 1988; Zeyl et al., 2011; Ailli, 2011; Eyeghé, 2018) which have shown that sales force management consists of the recruitment, training, evaluation, remuneration and motivation of the company's sales agents. Furthermore, commercial performance in this area is measured by managers through the revenue generated in their activities as well as the results generated from these various activities. Furthermore, these managers also take into account the evolution of the number and loyalty of their clients when measuring the commercial performance of their business.

It should also be noted that the influence of customer orientation on commercial performance is strong, thus demonstrating the importance of customers in achieving better commercial performance. The more brokers adopt customer orientation, the more commercially efficient they are. Customers constitute a key asset for these businesses, which benefit from satisfying their needs. This demonstrates

the strategic relevance of customer orientation. Customer orientation presents itself as a strategic resource allowing managers in this field to develop the ability to understand and respond to customer needs, which promotes improved commercial performance. This result supports previous research (Pekovic and Rolland, 2012; Tsapi and Tchunte, 2006; Gafa, 2020) suggesting that customer orientation is a factor that drives business performance, particularly in developing countries.

It should also be noted that the coefficient of determination for this regression is high ($R^2 = 0.418$), demonstrating that the model fits well with the various data in the study.

The research results reveal that customer orientation positively and significantly influences sales performance through sales force management. This demonstrates that sales force management plays a mediating role in the relationship between customer orientation and sales performance. This result supports previous studies (Gotteland et al., 2007; Zhu and Nakata 2007; Pekovic and Rolland, 2012, Doucouré et al., 2019, and Gafa, 2019), which demonstrated the existence of mediating variables between customer orientation and sales performance. It should also be noted that the mediating effect of compensation between customer orientation and sales performance is the strongest, followed by that of motivation. This shows that sales agents' compensation, followed by their work motivation, are dimensions of sales force management that most effectively convey the influence of customer orientation on the sales performance of insurance company intermediaries. Furthermore, the other three dimensions, namely training, recruitment, and evaluation, also convey the influence of customer orientation on sales performance, but with a lesser influence. This supports previous work showing the importance of compensation and motivation in achieving objectives (Fournier, 2016; Ailli, 2011).

CONCLUSION

Nous Through this research, we used an empirical model to evaluate the direct link between customer orientation and the sales performance of intermediaries and then establish the mediating role of sales force management in this relationship. Using regression tests and Hayes' PROCESS macro in SPSS, we were able to demonstrate, on the one hand, that customer orientation influences sales performance and, on the other, that this relationship is partially mediated by sales force management.

From a theoretical perspective, this research improves our understanding of the mechanisms by which customer orientation diffuses in small businesses, specifically insurance brokers, and its implications for their sales performance. Indeed, to our knowledge, no research has previously focused on the mediating role of sales force management in the relationship between customer orientation

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and the sales performance of insurance company intermediaries, particularly in developing countries. It should be noted that the concepts of customer orientation and commercial performance have been the subject of several conceptualizations in the context of large and medium-sized companies, particularly in developed countries. However, only a few rare studies have focused on the study of these concepts in small structures in developing countries. It should also be noted that the results of the confirmatory factor analysis and the validation of these results through good reliability and good adjustment of the measurement model of customer orientation and commercial performance therefore confirm the presence of these phenomena among managers of brokerage firms. The results of our research expand on previous work (Gotteland et al., 2007; Zhu and Nakata, 2007; Pekovic and Rolland, 2012, Doucouré et al., 2019 and Gafa, 2019) in that they indicate not only that customer orientation improves the sales performance of these small businesses, but also that sales force management mediates the relationship between customer orientation and sales performance. Furthermore, the results of this research also reveal that compensation and motivation are the dimensions of sales force management that most mediate the relationship between customer orientation and sales performance.

From a methodological perspective, it should be noted that for all the instruments used, we relied on a rigorous approach to ensure their reliability and validity.

Furthermore, collecting data from different managers in different functions and regions allowed us to diversify and enrich the information on customer orientation, sales force management, and sales performance.

From a managerial perspective, it is clear that customer orientation is a strategic resource that allows managers to develop the ability to understand and respond to customer needs. This research informs managers about the importance of customer orientation, which is a key factor in sales performance. To this end, to improve their sales performance, SME managers must not only implement customer orientation but also implement sales force management while placing greater emphasis on compensation and motivation. Therefore, adopting customer orientation with a sound sales compensation and motivation policy will enable managers to improve the sales performance of their institutions. This confirms, on the one hand, the strategic relevance of customer orientation, in line with previous empirical studies conducted on the subject (Zhu and Nakata, 2007; Singh and Ranchhod, 2004), and on the other hand, highlights the importance of compensation and motivation, which are the means to direct the sales force's activity towards achieving specific company objectives (Fournier, 2016; Ailli, 2011).

Although the results reveal that the coefficients are low for training, recruitment, and evaluation, it should be emphasized that brokers in the region will produce more sales

performance by recruiting competent salespeople with high self-confidence, by regularly training salespeople in new effective sales techniques, and by conducting qualitative and quantitative evaluations of sales agents' adoption of customer orientation.

Despite the various contributions of this research, we adopted the supply-side perspective. Future studies could be conducted by adopting a supply-side perspective as well as a demand-side perspective to better understand the various concepts.

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